

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP3

NA2 – Dissemination, Communication, and Collaboration

Deliverable D3.6

D-NA2.3b Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Beneficiary in Charge: European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories (DERlab)

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7967503](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7967503)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Deliverable Number:	D3.6
Deliverable Full Title:	D-NA2.3b Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls
Deliverable Short Title:	Summary TA Calls
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-D36-SummaryTACalls-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	European Distributed Energy Resources Laboratories (DERlab)
Report Version:	v1.5
Contractual Date:	30/04/2023
Report Submission Date:	24/05/2023
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	M. Setakhr (DERlab)
Co-author(s):	—
Keywords:	Communication, Dissemination, Networking, Trans-national Access, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	_ draft, _ final, _x_ submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
20/03/2023	v1.0	M.Setakhr (DERlab)	First document structure, input and draft for review
09/05/2023	v1.1	E. Rodriguez (TECNALIA)	Input, review, and suggestions for improvement
12/05/2023	v1.2	I. Gilbert (OCT), E. Rikos (CRES)	Internal review
15/05/2023	v1.3	M.Setakhr (DERlab)	Reviewers' comments implemented
16/05/2023	v1.4	E. Mrakotsky (AIT)	Language and grammar review
24/05/2023	v1.5	T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	8
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. Lab Access Calls Timeline	9
3. Lab Access Dissemination Material and Channels	10
3.1 Project Website	10
3.2 Flyer.....	11
3.3 Newsletter	11
3.4 Social Networks.....	11
3.5 Presentation Slides	13
4. Consortium's Dissemination of Lab Access Calls	14
5. Outcomes of Lab Access Calls Dissemination.....	17
6. Conclusions	18
References	19
Appendix A: Project Website.....	20
Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page	21
Appendix C: Project Flyer.....	22
Appendix D: Latest Project Newsletter	23
Appendix E: Lab Access Slide.....	24

List of Figures

Figure 1: Pageviews of the Trans-national Access (TA) subpage.	10
Figure 2: Example of the call announcement on LinkedIn.	12
Figure 3: Example of TA updates on Twitter.	13
Figure 4: Example of exposure on Twitter during TA Call 8.	13
Figure 5: ERIGrid 2.0 followers by organisation type.	18

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the consortium's dissemination efforts.....	14
Table 2: Outcomes of promotion through channels.....	17

List of Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
MTR	Mid-Term Review
NA	Networking Activities
PoC	Person of Contact
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTD	Research and Technology Development
TA	Trans-national Access
USP	User Selection Panel
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

In this document, the efforts of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium for the dissemination of the Trans-national Access in the time frame from 1 April 2022 until 30 April 2023 are reported, as well as the outcome of these efforts for TA Calls 5-8.

The documentation for Trans-national Access dissemination includes specific details about the materials and channels used, along with examples of activities that have been carried out. The channels used for disseminating information about the Trans-national Access program include the project website, various social media platforms, the project newsletter, and presentation slides.

In addition to the dissemination activities undertaken in WP3-NA2 led by DERlab as Work Package Leader, the report contains a brief overview of other partners' activities for the dissemination of ERIGrid 2.0's Trans-national Access programme.

Finally, the report provides details on the number of Trans-national Access proposals received for each call and the success rate of each dissemination channel. Based on this information, the report draws conclusions about the effectiveness of each channel. Finally, the report concludes by discussing the lessons learnt from the project and the measures that will be taken to promote the Trans-national Access program going forward, taking into account the project's progress to date and the established goals.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is the second summary report on TA dissemination activities of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It presents a summary of the efforts for the promotion of TA opportunities undertaken by DERlab as the Work Package Leader (WPL) of Work Package (WP) 3 – Networking Activities (NA) 2 as well as the rest of the consortium members. This deliverable also presents the marketing materials that have been developed and the channels that have been used to ensure the effective promotion of this activity.

Within its TAs, ERIGrid 2.0 offers external users free access to the Research Infrastructures (RIs) of the consortium partners, including funding for travel expenses, accommodation, subsistence costs, as well as scientific and dissemination support. This offer is primarily intended to benefit individuals and organisations in the research, academic, and industrial sectors focused on power system testing, smart grids, and energy systems. Through this activity, research projects in compliance with European Research and Technology Developments (RTDs) priorities and with the prospect of social impact and impact on European Union (EU) industry are supported. The TA programme aims to support new smart energy solutions and the development of an integrated European RI (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019).

As a set of channels and a significant following on each of them have been achieved in the predecessor project ERIGrid, ERIGrid 2.0 decided to continue using these accounts in the new project after necessary re-adjustment and re-branding. This enabled the consortium to ensure the transfer of best practices between the projects, maintaining momentum and effectively reaching the target audience.

Furthermore, it was decided within the consortium to use the term “Lab Access” for public promotion outside the project, as it is more comprehensive than the term “TA” for project-external persons.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 introduces the timeline for the TA calls. Section 3 presents materials and channels established for the promotion and how they have been used. Section 4 provides an overview of activities performed by consortium members. Section 5 presents the outcomes of the activities. The report is concluded in Section 6. Finally, images of the developed and used dissemination and marketing material are provided in Appendix A, Appendix B, Appendix C, Appendix D and Appendix E.

2 Lab Access Calls Timeline

The ERIGrid 2.0 TA programme is organised into three-month time windows, during which external users can submit their applications for lab access. The calls are launched every four months, with one calendar month reserved between the closing date of the previous call and the opening date of the next call.

The current report covers the time frame of the following TA calls and therefore presents the promotion efforts made during and between these:

- Call 5: 1 February 2022 – 30 April 2022
- Call 6: 1 June 2022 – 31 August 2022
- Call 7: 1 October 2022 – 31 December 2022
- Call 8: 1 February 2023 – 30 April 2023

3 Lab Access Dissemination Material and Channels

This section is about the materials and channels that ERIGrid 2.0 are using as promotional tools for the TA opportunities: the project website, the project flyer, the newsletter, the promotion on social networks, as well as the general presentation slides.

3.1 Project Website

The primary source of public information about ERIGrid 2.0, including its activities and results, can be found on the project website¹. The website gives significant coverage to the TA program, with a separate page created specifically for providing comprehensive and accessible information about it. The consortium has taken great care to offer as much assistance as possible to individuals interested in applying (see Appendix A). The dedicated lab access subpage² provides valuable information for potential applicants, including important details that can help guide them through the application process:

- General information about the TA, its target audience and the type of support offered by the programme,
- Timeline of the past and upcoming TA calls,
- Complete overview of the available facilities, with the option to filter them according to one of the categories: “Transient Power System Dynamics and Control Validation” or “Smart Energy Systems Integration and Validation”,
- Step-by-step instructions on how potential users can submit their applications
- Selection criteria,
- Relevant documents or necessary templates: lab access guide, proposal template, link to the proposal submission platform, contract model, test canvas template, and report template, and
- FAQ section, regularly updated based on the ongoing communication with applicants.

At the time of writing the TA subpage gathered nearly 40,000 pageviews during the last 500 days as outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pageviews of the TA subpage.

¹<https://erigrd2.eu>

²<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access>

Each of the available facilities in the overview on this page is linked to an individual page with detailed information about the RI provided at the corresponding facility, offered services, lab access conditions and any further relevant details, including videos and pictures. Furthermore, each lab page contains a contact form to enable potential applicants to ask any questions they may have. The submitted forms are automatically sent to the Person of Contact (PoC) of the corresponding labs. An example of a lab page is given in Appendix B.

Additionally, relevant for the TA and cross-linked from the TA subpage are the following two subpages:

- “*User Projects*³” presenting the list of implemented TA user projects, and
- “*Selection Panel*⁴” presenting the list of the User Selection Panel (USP) members for the purposes of transparency and for applicants to be able to indicate possible conflicts of interest in their applications.

As the number of user projects grows, the consortium is preparing a dedicated subpage entitled “Success Stories” to showcase successful examples of TA user research. This measure will contribute to the dissemination of the results as set out in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) and to attract even more potential TA users.

3.2 Flyer

The project flyer (see Appendix C) includes information about the TA program. This was done to ensure that the program receives proper attention and promotion along with other project aspects. The flyer provides essential information on the TA program, such as general details, the application timeline, and references to additional information. It has been designed to be distributed and shared at various events, conferences, trade fairs, meetings, and networking opportunities.

3.3 Newsletter

At the start of the project, a newsletter template was created to maintain consistency. This newsletter contains the most recent updates and opportunities, such as information about the TA program and related details, and is sent out to over 600 subscribers on a regular basis. Ten newsletters⁵ have been released to date, out of which nine advertised TA and corresponding calls. The average open rate across the newsletters varies between about 30% and 40%, which is considered a good rate for newsletters. An example of the latest newsletter, which was sent out in March, shows the promotion of the TA Call 5 in Appendix D.

3.4 Social Networks

ERIGrid 2.0 uses social networks *LinkedIn*⁶ and *Twitter*⁷ for general project promotion and TA dissemination.

³<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects>

⁴<https://erigrd2.eu/selection-panel>

⁵<https://erigrd2.eu/resources#newsletters>

⁶<https://www.linkedin.com/company/erigrd-project>

⁷<https://twitter.com/ERIGrid>

At the time of writing, ERIGrid 2.0 has over 1,850 followers on LinkedIn and over 500 followers on Twitter. All past calls were advertised extensively, including:

- Announcement of the opening of TA Call 8 (see Figure 2),
- Three sponsored campaigns on LinkedIn, which collectively gathered over 80,000 impressions and over 300 clicks through to the TA subpage, and
- Regular updates highlighting the RI of each facility.

Figure 2: Example of the call announcement on LinkedIn.

Examples of TA updates on Twitter and the reached engagement are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Example of TA updates on Twitter.

Figure 4: Example of exposure on Twitter during TA Call 8.

3.5 Presentation Slides

The project consortium has developed a project presentation for disseminating information at relevant events and conferences. One of the slides in the presentation is dedicated to showcasing the TA programme. This slide includes a map displaying the available facilities, their logos, and a reference for obtaining more information. By incorporating the TA program into the presentation, the project gains greater exposure as project partners participate in numerous events where the ERIGrid 2.0 target audience is present.

4 Consortium's Dissemination of Lab Access Calls

Table 1 provides an overview of the dissemination efforts undertaken by the consortium.

Table 1: Overview of the consortium's dissemination efforts.

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
DERlab	Updates and posts	Social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Regular and ongoing	Research, academia, industry; ca. 1,800 followers
DERlab	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research; broad international networks (ISGAN Annex 5 SIRFN, ETIP SNET, EERA JP Smart Grids, BRIDGE)
OFFIS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channel LinkedIn	During TA Calls, after TA completion at the SESA laboratory	Research institutes, universities, companies ca. 700 followers
CRES	Updates and posts	Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
CRES	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies, including the consortium of GIFT (H2020)
CRES	Promotion	Presentation	During bilateral meetings	Industry, SMEs
JRC	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	European research institutions and private companies operating in the energy sector
VTT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
VTT	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
VTT	Workshops, Tutorials, Webinars, Fairs	Presentation	ERIGrid-CINELDI 2023, IEEE SmartGridComm 2022, Nanyang Technological University	Research institutes, universities, companies
AIT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website, AIT Social Media Channel	During TA calls, posts during lab access	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
AIT	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing, especially directed to former users and their institutions	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
AIT	Conferences, Workshops, Tutorials, Webinars, Fairs	Presentation	DigiSect 2022 & 2023, OSMSES 2023, DERlab GA, IEEE SMC 2022, IRED 2022, PCIM 2022, InterSolar 2022, CIGRE Session 2022, IEA ISGAN-SIRFN Meetings, ERN 2022, etc.	Research institutes, universities, companies
ICCS	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
ICCS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channel LinkedIn	During TA calls, posts after TA completion	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
ICCS	Seminars, Panel Sessions, Tutorials	Presentation	IEEE PELS IIT BBS Student Chapter, OSMSES 2023	Research institutes, universities, companies
ICCS	Stakeholder events	Presentation	CCRSB Stakeholders event	Research institutes, universities, companies
TECNALIA	Promotion	Presentation	During multiple visits to TECNALIA's facilities	Research institutes, universities, industrial companies
TECNALIA	TA Programme explanation	Phone and Email	Direct interactions with partners and customers	Research institutes, universities, industrial companies
TECNALIA	Promotion	Presentation	FUTURED (Spanish Electrical Grid Platform) events	Research institutes, universities, industrial companies
TECNALIA	Promotion	Presentation	PhD Seminar, 24-28 Oct 2022, Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas, Bogotá (Colombia)	Colombian Universities
RSE	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels, LinkedIn	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
RSE	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
OCT	Promotion	Presentation	During different visits to UDEX	Several industrial companies
OCT	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
UCY-FOSS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels, LinkedIn	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
UCY-FOSS	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
SINTEF	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
SINTEF	Updates and posts	Social media (WhatsApp)	During TA calls	Regular message with link to TA access to researchers groups
SINTEF	Updates and posts	Webinars, meetings	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies

5 Outcomes of Lab Access Calls Dissemination

In the four TA calls reported in this document, the consortium received 58 proposals. Based on preliminary estimations, that number amounts to approximately 547 access days (32% of the objective in the Description of Action (DoA)) for Calls 5-7 (Call 8 is not yet evaluated). Having completed seven calls and with the eighth call in evaluation at the time of writing, the consortium foresees another two calls until the project end, amounting to 10 calls overall in the project runtime. Assuming the consortium keeps up the rate of received TA proposals, the target of access days can be achieved.

The DoA set out the goal of at least 25% of the executed user projects must be carried out with industry participation. The progress estimation upon completion of the first seven calls lies at approximately 20%.

For effective dissemination of TA calls, it is important for the consortium to know which of the used promotion channels result in the most outcomes in terms of number of submitted proposals in each call. For that purpose, the questions about how the applicants had learned about the TA was included in the TA application procedure. The collected answers are summarised in Table 2, which presents the outcomes of dissemination through specific channels. Applicants frequently indicate multiple sources of their initial knowledge of ERIGrid 2.0, therefore the number of proposals for all sources indicated for a specific call may collectively exceed the number of actual proposals received in the call.

Table 2: Outcomes of promotion through channels

	Call 5 11 proposals	Call 6 6 proposals	Call 7 25 proposals	Call 8 16 proposals
Personal recommendation by project partner	2	2	10	6
Previous connection with ERIGrid	5	2	4	6
Website	1	-	2	2
Social media	1	1	2	1
Involved in ERIGrid 2.0	2	-	5	-
Project partner email promotion	-	-	-	-
Event	-	1	6	1
PowerGlobe Forum	-	-	-	-
Newsletter	-	-	-	-

As seen from the collected answers, the highest number of proposals, collectively for Calls 5 to 8, as well as for each call, came as a result of individual promotion directed to personal contacts. The second most efficient way to receive proposals is through a previous connection and past knowledge of the predecessor project ERIGrid. The following most effective channels are involvement within ERIGrid 2.0 and through events and conferences.

6 Conclusions

It can be concluded from the outcomes of the previous TA calls that the most successful means of obtaining proposals is through individual partners' promotion and personal recommendations to potential applicants. Therefore, the consortium will put more focus on this channel in their further promotion efforts. As more ERIGrid 2.0 events are being organised later on in the project, there will be more opportunities for the partners for such networking activities.

Furthermore, according to the recommendations resulting from the Mid-Term Review (MTR) of the ERIGrid 2.0 project (i.e., on 02/02/2022), more focus should be put on the general dissemination of the work and on the promotion of the access to the lab facilities, beyond the project partners and their direct research communities. Thanks to social media analytics (particularly LinkedIn), it can be seen that the largest part of ERIGrid 2.0's audience comes from research and academia (see Figure 5). As the project is already quite established within the research community, more effort will be put into reaching a wider audience such as the general public or policymakers. This will allow the project to gain more visibility and awareness and thus increase the project's impact.

Figure 5: ERIGrid 2.0 followers by organisation type.

A good way to reach a wider audience is by offering engaging content. One example of a measure that has been put in place to address this is the creation of "Success Story" templates, in order to share, in an easy-to-read way, the positive research experiences and results enabled by the TA calls. These will be shared and promoted through the project website, social media channels, newsletters and at various relevant events and conferences.

References

ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Appendix A: Project Website

GET FREE ACCESS TO LEADING SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS AND SERVICES

ERIGrid 2.0 invites all interested engineers involved in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems to receive free funding to access the best laboratories of Europe and perform their own experimental research. There are two kinds of lab access services available in ERIGrid 2.0:

FREE ACCESS TO 21 PHYSICAL LABS

Physical free access to our laboratories can be performed on-site at the location of the lab or remotely if the infrastructure allows. To get this access you need to apply as described below and to be selected by the Independent User Selection Panel (USP).

If your application is successful, you will receive funding for your research stay at the location of the laboratory you selected, completely covering the following expenses:

- Travelling
- Accommodation
- All lab operation costs and physical lab access to ERIGrid 2.0 testing and simulation facilities
- Access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grid and energy systems, such as: power system components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power Controller. Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) and others.

FREE ACCESS TO 10 VIRTUAL FACILITIES

The access to the virtual facilities requires no specific application and user proposals are not submitted to a selection process.

You can access and start using the free virtual services right away taking the following points into account:

- The provided virtual data, services and resources are openly and freely available under open access licenses through communication networks.
- Access to virtual services allows for a quick, easy and casual access to existing virtual resources by eliminating administrative obstacles.
- Users can try the provided virtual services without obligations.
- No individual support or supervision is offered to the users.

APPLY NOW UNTIL 30 APRIL, 2023!

Please note that applications close automatically on the date of the deadline, and no late applications can be accepted.

Schedule of calls for lab access proposals:

- 1st call: 1 October 2020 – 31 December 2020 (closed)
- 2nd call: 1 February 2021 – 30 April 2021 (closed)
- 3rd call: 1 June 2021 – 31 August 2021 (closed)
- 4th call: 1 October 2021 – 31 December 2021 (closed)
- 5th call: 1 February 2022 – 30 April 2022 (closed)
- 6th call: 1 June 2022 – 31 August 2022 (closed)
- 7th call: 1 October 2022 – 31 December 2022 (closed)
- 8th call: 1 February 2023 – 30 April 2023
- 9th call: 1 June 2023 – 31 August 2023
- 10th call: 1 October 2023 – 31 December 2023

[Subscribe to Newsletter](#) | To stay informed about the lab access programme and detailed descriptions of the facilities and services, bookmark this page or just subscribe to the ERIGrid newsletter to receive all the updates directly in your inbox.

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS APPLICATION PROCESS

Identify your experimental needs: empirical topic and testing/validation goals

Select potential labs (up to 2) which are suitable for your topic

Build up your team or decide to apply as an individual user

Write the proposal using this template

Your proposal will be evaluated by independent reviewers from this list – Please point out any names that may involve a conflict of interest in the proposal submission system

Register yourself in the proposal submission system and submit your proposal - list all user group members in the submission system (same list as in the proposal)

1 Lab Access Guide

2 Proposal Template

3 Proposal Submission

4 Contract Model

5 Test Canvas Template

6 Report Template

ERIGrid 2.0 partners offer a wide range of installations and competences to assist successful applicants with conducting experiments. Such a common framework of applied smart grid expertise will accelerate the development of an integrated pan-European research infrastructure.

Thomas Strasser (AIT)
Coordinator of ERIGrid 2.0

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS SELECTION CRITERIA

Your proposal for physical lab access must meet the following criteria:

- Scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach
- Prospect of knowledge enhancement at the research infrastructures
- Competences and organization of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of requested access
- Compliance with European RTD policies and priorities; prospect of social impact and impact on EU industry. New users, young researchers, female researchers are especially welcome.

The evaluation will be performed by the User Selection Panel, an international independent group of experts with diverse profiles (academia, industry) covering the different domains of the smart energy systems (power systems, ICT, etc.). In parallel, a technical and economic feasibility check for the potential lab implementation will be done by the addressed ERIGrid 2.0 infrastructures.

PHYSICAL LABS AND VIRTUAL SERVICES

Access to physical labs can be on-site or remote, depending on the conditions of specific laboratories. To know if remote access can be organised in your case, please contact the laboratory staff through corresponding subpages below.

ALL	ON-SITE AND REMOTE TRANSIENT POWER SYSTEM DYNAMICS AND CONTROL VALIDATION	ON-SITE AND REMOTE SMART ENERGY SYSTEMS INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION	VIRTUAL FACILITIES

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS FAQ

- WHAT IS A "USER GROUP" AND HOW MANY PERSONS CAN BE PART OF IT?
Applications are submitted by User Groups (UG). A UG is a team of one or more researchers from one or more institutions/companies which is led by a so-called user group leader. Despite the fact that the user group implementing the project in the lab is normally composed by two researchers, one single researcher is also allowed. Unless fully justified, the maximum number must be always kept to three researchers getting access to the lab.
- WHAT IS THE TYPICAL DURATION OF A PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS USER PROJECT?
- DO THE APPLICANT(S) NEED TO CONTACT THE PREFERRED LAB DURING THE PROPOSAL PREPARATION?
- CAN I APPLY FOR A LAB LOCATED IN MY COUNTRY?
- CAN UK USER GROUPS STILL APPLY?
- CAN NON-EU PROJECTS APPLY?
- PLAGIARISM CHECK OF PROPOSALS
- WHEN WILL I BE INFORMED IF MY PROPOSAL WAS APPROVED?
- WHAT SHOULD I DO IF MY PROPOSAL IS APPROVED?
- WILL A CONTRACT TEMPLATE BE MADE AVAILABLE?
- WILL I HAVE TO PUBLICISE THE RESULTS OF MY PROJECT?
- WHAT HAPPENS AFTER THE ACCESS?
- ARE THERE ANY EXAMPLES OF PERFORMED USER PROJECTS?
- HOW DOES COVID-19 PANDEMIC INFLUENCE THE LAB ACCESS PROGRAMME?
- STILL HAVE SOME QUESTIONS, HOW CAN I CONTACT YOU?

Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page

SMART GRID COMMUNICATION LABORATORY (HEDNO)

The Smart Grid Communication Laboratory (SGC-Lab) constitutes a part of the Voice and Data Communication Section of the Information Technology & Telecommunications Department of HEDNO. It aims to develop and administer the communication network of HEDNO in the framework of smart grid communications.

More specifically, the laboratory's scope is the evaluation of communication technologies suitable for remote monitoring and remote control of the Greek distribution grid. Moreover, the SGC-Lab seeks to establish research and laboratory facilities to provide added value operational guidelines and information to production systems (Operational and Information Technology).

Location: HEDNO - Athens, Greece

www.deddie.gr

+ DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

+ SERVICES OFFERED

+ DESCRIPTION OF THE ORGANIZATION

+ LAB ACCESS CONDITIONS OFFERED BY HEDNO

Appendix C: Project Flyer

FREE PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL LAB ACCESS

The ERIGrid 2.0 project invites all interested engineers in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and smart energy to receive free funding to access the best laboratories and services of Europe for their own experimental research. Physical lab access can be organised either on-site or remotely. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 provides virtual access to 8 facilities and services without applications required.

USERS WILL RECEIVE:

- on-site or remote access to 21 first-class laboratories or application-free virtual access to 8 services of ERIGrid partners
- in case of physical access: funding for their complete research stay at the location of the selected laboratory, including coverage of expenses for travelling, accommodation and lab operation costs
- access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grids and energy systems components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others
- opportunity to advance their own research and solutions
- working with the top smart grid and energy systems experts
- chance to impact EU industry
- promotion of their research through ERIGrid 2.0 channels

Find detailed descriptions of labs and services and all further details at erigrd2.eu/lab-access.

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

access virtual services anytime no application required

CONSORTIUM COORDINATED BY

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

@ERIGrid 2.0 Project

www.erigrd2.eu

Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620

Based on the results from the predecessor project ERIGrid-1, ERIGrid 2.0 will expand the research services and tools of research infrastructures for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

ABOUT

- ERIGrid 2.0: European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- 20 partners from research, academia and industry
- 21 first-class European labs provided to external users for free access on-site or remotely
- 8 facilities and services provided to external users for virtual access
- 13 European countries represented in the consortium
- Duration: 1 April 2020 – 30 September 2024
- Budget: €10M funded by the European Commission

ERIGrid 2.0 – European RI for Smart Grids, Smart Energy Systems, and Renewables Research

SUSTAINABLE, LOW-CARBON ENERGY POLICY

- 2015 Paris Agreement
- EU "Clean Energy for All Europeans" package
- EU Vision 2050

EU Energy Transition Goal: Creation of a low-carbon, secure, reliable, resilient, accessible, cost-efficient, and market-based pan-European integrated energy system

Goals:

- support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy systems approaches, concepts, and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account
- provide system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development

Networking Objectives:

- knowledge-exchange with other European smart grid and smart energy systems RIs
- knowledge transfer between researchers, technicians, and RI managers
- Open Access (OA) provision of achievements and reinforced collaboration with industry and energy utilities
- education of power and energy system professionals
- international collaboration and harmonization

Appendix D: Latest Project Newsletter

[View this email in your browser](#)

Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

European Research Infrastructure Supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll out - Second Edition

In this issue:

- [8th Lab Access Call open until 30 April 2023](#)
- [ERIGRID 2.0 supports the upcoming DigSect 2023 Workshop](#)
- [Meet us at the joint ERIGRID 2.0-HYPERRIDE booth at CIRED 2023](#)
- [ERIGRID 2.0 - CINELDI Workshop on 'ICT for automation in smart grid and its cybersecurity challenges' outcomes](#)
- [ERIGRID 2.0's many virtual facilities](#)
- [ERIGRID 2.0 presented at Smart Energy Events](#)
- [Latest Resources](#)

ERIGRID 2.0's many virtual facilities

ERIGRID 2.0 allows **free access to 10 virtual facilities**. The access to the virtual facilities requires no specific application and user proposals are not submitted to a selection process. One of these facilities is [RSE's DER-TF DataS](#) which is a platform that provides the access to historical and real-time data of a real Low Voltage microgrid. The infrastructure is composed by a time series database (TSDB) and an object storage (topology, assets, test case description) that is accessible through a web-interface that allows to explore the information at component and system level. [The Virtual Lab](#), another facility, is an online educational simulation tool that mimics the operation of the actual laboratory microgrid of EES lab of ICCS. A mathematical model of the laboratory microgrid has been developed along with a friendly GUI. The user can observe several variables (e.g., voltage, active power, reactive power etc.) and perform several actions (e.g. change the power factor of the inverter). The simulation tool includes two different laboratory setups and corresponding experiments: voltage control, and microgrid operation.

Find out about many more in the Virtual Facilities on the [Lab Access page](#).

Apply for Free Lab Access By 30 April 2023

Up until 30 April 2023, ERIGRID 2.0 welcomes applications for research stays and remote lab access to ERIGRID 2.0 testing facilities within the frame of the 8th Lab Access call.

FREE ACCESS TO SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

Remote access can be arranged depending on the conditions at the lab and the applicant's research requirements. Successful applicants will be granted funding covering their travelling expenses, accommodation, all lab operation costs and

ERIGRID 2.0 presented at Smart Energy Events

On 10 November 2022 in Ispra (IT), ERIGRID 2.0 was presented by Thomas Strasser ([AIT](#)) at the JRC workshop "Supporting a local energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks", during the session "Internet-of-labs supporting the energy transition".

Latest Resources

- [Testing-oriented development and open-source documentation of interoperable benchmark models for energy systems](#)
- [Overview of the ERIGRID 2.0 Smart Grid and Energy Systems Research Infrastructure Activities and Access Opportunities](#)
- [An Introduction to Working with the SmartEST Sim Lab](#)
- [Find all other resources in ERIGRID 2.0 Zenodo community here](#)

Keep up with ERIGRID 2.0 news

Appendix E: Lab Access Slide

The slide features a map of Europe with green highlights in Scandinavia, Germany, and parts of France and Italy. Two red banners are overlaid on the map: "apply every 3 months for physical lab access" and "access virtual services anytime no application required". To the right, there are four images: a building, a control room, a server room, and a technician working on equipment. Below these images is a grid of logos for various research institutions. At the bottom left is the ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium logo and EU H2020 Programme GA No. 870620. At the bottom right is the text "Project Overview and Research Infrastructure Access Possibilities" and the number "8".

ERIGRID 2.0
Connecting European
Smart Grid Infrastructures

apply every 3 months for
physical lab access

access virtual services anytime
no application required

<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

© The ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium
EU H2020 Programme GA No. 870620

Project Overview and Research Infrastructure Access Possibilities

8

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2023 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

